

STRUCTURAL CLASSES OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation: This comparative study delves into the structural classes of verbs in English and Uzbek, exploring their morphological, syntactic, and semantic dimensions. In English, verbs span diverse categories including transitive, intransitive, copular, auxiliary, modal, and phrasal verbs, each embodying distinct syntactic and semantic functions. Conversely, Uzbek verbs manifest as transitive, intransitive, reflexive, and causative, reflecting typological nuances within the Turkic language family. Morphologically, both languages employ various strategies for encoding tense, aspect, mood, person, and number. Syntactically, English and Uzbek verbs exhibit divergent word order patterns and auxiliary usage. Semantically, verbs in both languages convey rich layers of meaning, encapsulating actions, states, and modality. This comparative analysis sheds light on linguistic typology, facilitating insights into cross-linguistic variation and the implications for language pedagogy, translation studies, and linguistic research.

Keywords: Verbs, Structural Classes, English, Uzbek, Morphology, Syntax, Semantics, Typology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu qiyosiy tadqiqot ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi fe'llarning strukturaviy sinflarini o'rganadi, ularning morfologik, sintaktik va semantik jihatlarini o'rganadi. Ingliz tilida fe'llar turli toifalarni o'z ichiga oladi, shu jumladan o'tishli, o'timsiz, kopular, yordamchi, modal va frazeologik fe'llar, har biri alohida sintaktik va semantik funksiyalarni o'zida mujassam etgan. Aksincha, o'zbek tilidagi fe'llar turkiy tillar oilasi doirasidagi tipologik turlarni aks ettiruvchi o'timli, o'timsiz, refleksiv va sabab sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Morfologik jihatdan ikkala til ham zamon, aspekt, kayfiyat, shaxs va sonni kodlash uchun turli strategiyalardan foydalanadi. Sintaktik jihatdan ingliz va o'zbek fe'llari turlicha so'z tartibi qoliplari va yordamchi qo'llanishni namoyon qiladi. Semantik jihatdan har ikkala tildagi fe'llar boy ma'no qatlamlarini, qamrab oluvchi harakat, holat va modallikni bildiradi.

Ushbu qiyosiy tahlil lingvistik tipologiyaga oydinlik kiritib, tillararo o‘zgaruvchanlik va til pedagogikasi, tarjimashunoslik va lingvistik tadqiqotlarga ta’sirini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Fe’llar, Strukturaviy sinflar, Ingliz tili, O‘zbek tili, Morfologiya, Sintaksis, Semantika, Tipologiya.

INTRODUCTION

Verbs are essential components of any language, serving as the core element in expressing actions, events, and states of being. Understanding the structural classes of verbs is crucial for linguistic analysis, as it provides insights into how languages organize and express different types of actions and events. This article embarks on a comprehensive comparative journey between English and Uzbek, two linguistically distinct languages, to unravel the structural classes of verbs, their morphological manifestations, syntactic behaviors, semantic implications, and the underlying typological influences.

Structural Classes of Verbs in English

English verbs traverse a diverse landscape of structural categories, each delineating unique syntactic and semantic functions. In English, verbs can be classified into various structural classes based on their behavior and properties. One common classification is based on their morphology and syntactic behavior. English verbs can be categorized into regular verbs, irregular verbs, modal verbs, auxiliary verbs, transitive verbs, intransitive verbs, phrasal verbs, copular, and so on.

Transitive verbs, such as "eat, " necessitate a direct object for completeness, whereas intransitive verbs like "sleep" stand independently without direct objects. For example, in the sentence "She reads a book, " the verb "reads" is transitive as it takes the direct object "a book. "

- Transitive verbs require a direct object to complete their meaning (e. g. , "She eats an apple").

- Intransitive verbs, on the other hand, do not require a direct object to complete their meaning (e. g. , "He sleeps").

Copular verbs, exemplified by "be" establish connections between subjects and their complements, conveying states or attributes.

- Copular verbs, also known as linking verbs, connect the subject to a subject complement (e. g. , "She is happy").

Auxiliary verbs, encompassing modal and non-modal varieties, facilitate the expression of tense, aspect, mood, and modality.

- Auxiliary verbs, such as "be, " "have, " and "do, " (e. g. , "She has eaten").

Modal verbs in English include can, could, may, might, shall, should, will, would, must, and ought to. These verbs express various degrees of possibility, necessity, permission, and obligation (e. g. , "He can swim").

Phrasal verbs consist of a main verb and one or more particles (prepositions or adverbs) that together convey a specific meaning different from the individual words. Phrasal verbs, combining a verb with one or more particles, exhibit idiomatic meanings, as in "look up. "

- Phrasal verbs consist of a main verb and one or more particles, forming a unit of meaning distinct from its constituent parts (e. g. , "She put off the meeting").

Regular verbs in English follow a predictable pattern when conjugated in different tenses. For example, the verb "walk" follows the pattern of walk-walked-walked for its past simple and past participle forms.

Irregular verbs, on the other hand, do not follow a standard pattern and have unique forms for their past tense and past participle. An example is the verb "go" with the forms go-went-gone.

Verbs are essential elements in both English and Uzbek languages, responsible for conveying actions, events, or states. In linguistic studies, verbs are often classified into structural classes based on their morphological and syntactic properties. English and Uzbek, despite belonging to different language families (Indo-European and Altaic, respectively), exhibit interesting patterns in the categorization of verbs. This research paper aims to explore the structural classes of verbs in English and Uzbek, emphasizing the unique characteristics and classifications in each language.

Structural Classes of Verbs in Uzbek

In Uzbek, verbs also exhibit various structural classes based on their morphology and syntactic behavior. Uzbek verbs exhibit a different set of structural classes compared to English. Uzbek verbs can be classified into regular verbs, irregular verbs, transitive verbs, intransitive verbs, reflexive verbs, causative verbs, and so on. Conversely, Uzbek verbs embrace a distinct array of structural classes, reflecting the language's Turkic lineage.

Regular verbs in Uzbek follow specific patterns when conjugated in different tenses and moods. For instance, the verb "o'qimoq" (to read) has the forms o'qiyman, o'qidim, o'qimoqchiman for its present tense, past tense, and future tense, respectively. Irregular verbs in Uzbek have unique forms for different tenses and moods, deviating from the regular patterns.

Transitive verbs in Uzbek, similar to English, require a direct object to complete their meaning in a sentence. For example, in the sentence "U kitobni o'qidi" (He read the book), the verb "o'qidi" is transitive as it takes the direct object "kitobni" (the book).

Intransitive verbs in Uzbek do not require a direct object and can express a complete idea on their own (e. g. , "U uyda").

Transitive verbs, exemplified by "ko'rmoq" (to see), mandate direct objects for semantic coherence, while intransitive verbs like "uyquga ketmoq" (to fall asleep) operate independently.

Reflexive verbs in Uzbek indicate that the subject of the verb is also the object of the action. For example, the verb "yuvinoq" (to wash oneself) is reflexive in nature, reflecting the action back onto the subject.

Causative verbs in Uzbek express the idea of causing someone to do something. For instance, the verb form "o'qitir-" is used to indicate causing someone to read. Causative verbs, like "bolaga o'rgatmoq" (to teach a boy), (e. g. , "U meni uyga keltirdi").

Morphological and Syntactic Features

English verbs undergo intricate morphological transformations to encode tense, aspect, mood, person, and number. Suffixation, auxiliary verbs, and modal auxiliaries facilitate these morphosyntactic operations. Syntactically, English verbs exhibit subject-verb agreement, diverse word order permutations, and auxiliary usage for negation and question formation.

In Uzbek, verbs undergo morphological alterations through suffixation, vowel harmony, and agglutination to express tense, aspect, mood, person, and number. Syntactically, Uzbek verbs adhere to a subject-object-verb (SOV) word order, with auxiliary verbs employed for compound tenses and modal expressions.

METHOD

To conduct this comparative analysis, we first compiled a list of verbs from both languages, focusing on a variety of verb forms and functions. We then categorized the verbs into structural classes based on criteria such as transitivity, aspect, tense, and composition with auxiliaries. The structural classes identified in English include auxiliary verbs, transitive verbs, intransitive verbs, stative verbs, dynamic verbs, modal verbs, and phrasal verbs. In Uzbek, common structural classes consist of transitive verbs, intransitive verbs, reflexive verbs, causative verbs, passive verbs, and compound verbs. After categorizing the verbs, we compared the structural classes

in English and Uzbek languages, noting similarities and differences in how verbs are classified and used in sentence structures.

COMPARISON

In comparing the structural classes of verbs in English and Uzbek, we can observe some similarities and differences. Both languages have regular and irregular verbs that follow specific patterns or have unique forms for different tenses. Transitive and intransitive verbs exist in both languages, requiring a direct object or not, respectively. Modal verbs in English have similar counterparts in Uzbek that express possibility, necessity, and obligation. Auxiliary verbs in English serve a similar purpose to some verb forms in Uzbek that help in constructing various tenses and moods. Phrasal verbs in English also have equivalents in Uzbek that involve combining a main verb with particles to convey specific meanings.

SEMANTIC CONSIDERATIONS

Semantic nuances associated with different structural classes of verbs contribute to the overall meaning conveyed in English and Uzbek sentences. While some semantic roles may align across languages, others may be language-specific due to cultural and linguistic factors.

INFLUENCE OF LANGUAGE TYPOLOGY

The typological differences between English and Uzbek influence the organization and categorization of verbs. English, as an Indo-European language, exhibits typological features common to many other languages within the family. In contrast, Uzbek, as a Turkic language, displays typological characteristics specific to the Turkic language group.

RESULTS

In English, auxiliary verbs play a crucial role in expressing tense, aspect, and modality, often combining with main verbs to form complex verb phrases. Transitive verbs require a direct object to complete their meaning, while intransitive verbs do not have a direct object. Stative verbs describe states or conditions, while dynamic verbs express actions or processes. Modal verbs indicate possibility, necessity, or permission. Phrasal verbs consist of a main verb and one or more particles, creating idiomatic meanings.

In Uzbek, transitive verbs require an object to complete their meaning, similar to English. Intransitive verbs do not take objects and describe actions without direct recipients. Reflexive verbs in Uzbek denote actions performed by the subject on themselves. Causative verbs indicate causing something to happen, while passive

verbs highlight the recipient of the action. Compound verbs in Uzbek consist of a verb stem with added prefixes or suffixes, altering the meaning or aspect of the verb.

DISCUSSION

The structural classes of verbs in English and Uzbek exhibit both similarities and differences. Both languages categorize verbs based on transitivity, but Uzbek additionally distinguishes reflexive and causative verbs as separate categories. English relies on auxiliary verbs extensively to express various grammatical features, while Uzbek tends to use compound verbs for similar purposes.

In Uzbek, the causative verb form is particularly notable, allowing speakers to indicate causing an action to happen. This contrasts with English, where the causative aspect is often expressed through auxiliary verbs like 'make' or 'have.' The reflexive verb form in Uzbek also adds a unique feature not commonly found in English, reflecting the focus on self-directed actions.

Overall, the comparison of structural classes of verbs in English and Uzbek illuminates the diverse ways in which languages categorize and express actions, events, and states.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, verbs in English and Uzbek exhibit various structural classes based on their morphology and syntactic behavior. Understanding these classes is essential for mastering the grammar and syntax of each language. While there are similarities in the structural classes of verbs between English and Uzbek, they exhibit distinct features such as reflexive and causative verbs in Uzbek and extensive use of auxiliary and phrasal verbs in English. The structural classes of verbs in English and Uzbek exhibit both similarities and differences. While both languages categorize verbs based on syntactic and morphological properties, the specific classes and linguistic features vary due to the unique grammatical structures of each language. A comparative analysis of these structural classes enhances our understanding of linguistic diversity and the ways in which languages encode meaning through verbal expressions.

Studying the structural classes of verbs in different languages broadens our understanding of linguistic diversity and the nuanced ways in which languages express actions and states. Further research could explore how these structural classes impact sentence formation, meaning interpretation, and language learning processes. The comparative analysis of the structural classes of verbs in English and Uzbek unravels a tapestry of syntactic, semantic, and typological intricacies. By delving into these linguistic phenomena, scholars and language enthusiasts can deepen their

understanding of cross-linguistic variation and typological diversity, fostering enriched pedagogical approaches, sophisticated translation strategies, and nuanced linguistic analyses.

References:

1. Comrie, Bernard. (1985). *Tense*. Cambridge University Press.
2. Dahl, Östen. (2001). *The Growth and Maintenance of Linguistic Complexity*. John Benjamins Publishing.
3. Karimov, Aziz. (2010). *Uzbek Grammar*. Tashkent Publishing House.
4. Crystal, D. (2008). *A dictionary of linguistics and phonetics*. John Wiley & Sons.
5. Comrie, B. (1989). *Language universals and linguistic typology: Syntax and morphology (Vol. 2)*. University of Chicago Press.
6. Dalrymple, M. , & Nikolaeva, I. (2011). *Syntax of the World's Languages*. Cambridge University Press.
7. Lewis, M. P. , Simons, G. F. , & Fennig, C. D. (Eds.). (2015). *Ethnologue: Languages of the world*. SIL International.
8. Chelliah, S. (2018). *A Grammar of Spoken Uzbek*. Cambridge University Press.
9. Radford, A. (2004). *English Syntax: An Introduction*. Cambridge University Press.